

Flowering behavior of ratoons of F₂ rice segregates

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Photoperiod-sensitive traditional indicas such as FR13A and Achra 108/1 that flower in Mar-Apr at RRS, Chinsurah (22° 58'N) can be ratooned and will flower in Oct when daylength is similar (11 h to 11 h 30 min). Few traditional varieties show similar type of behavior.

We tested crosses of FR13A, Achra 108/1, IR36, and IR50 for flowering behavior of their ratoons when sown in November.

Seeds of the crosses were sown 15 Nov 1983 and transplanted in mid-Jan

Flowering behavior of F₂ segregates and their ratoons, Chinsurah, India, 1984.

Cross	Plants (no.)	Plants flowering in Mar-Apr (no.)	Ratooned plants flowering in Oct		Plants flowering in intermediate months ^a	
			No.	%	No.	%
FR13A/Achra 108/1	106	88	44	50	44	50
FR13A/IR36	106	102	42	41	60	59
FR13A/IR50	106	103	48	41	55	53
Achra 108/1/IR36	106	96	35	36	61	63
Achra 100/1/IR50	106	102	40	39	62	61
IR36/IR50	106	106	—	—	—	—

^a Jul-Sep.

1984. Plants that flowered in Apr were ratooned at the end of May, and remaining plants in vegetative stage were uprooted. Flowering behavior of ratooned plants was recorded. Plants that flowered between Jul and Sep and

in Oct were separated (see table). Of the plants obtained from different crosses, 36-50% flowered twice and fitted the desired behavior. However, crosses between photoperiod-insensitive types failed to produce desirable plants. \mathcal{L}

Effect of salinity on rice dry matter accumulation and sodium uptake

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Soil salinity constrains rice growth in parts of many countries. It is important to identify salt-tolerant rices and criteria for salt tolerance. We evaluated eight high yielding rice varieties with known levels of salt tolerance and sensitivity to

Table 1. Effect of salinity stress on dry matter production of rice varieties at peak tillering stage, West Bengal, India.^a

Variety	Dry matter production (g/pot) at ECe (mmho/cm) of		
	3.0 (control)	8.0	12.0
CSR-1	28	27 (2)	19 (31)
CSR-6	18	11 (39)	10 (46)
CST14-2	20	15 (27)	11 (43)
CST438-1	23	17 (29)	13 (44)
CST202-2	13	8 (43)	6 (53)
CST100-1	19	12 (36)	9 (56)
Jaya	18	10 (44)	7 (68)
M1-48	14	7 (51)	9 (75)

CD at P = 0.05

Variety = 0.442 g

Salinity = 0.270 g

Variety × salinity = 0.766 g

^a Figures in parentheses indicate reduction percentage over control.

quantify dry matter accumulation and the pattern of Na⁺ uptake. The experiment was at CSSRI in Canning.

Soil salinity levels (ECe 3, 8, and 12 mmho/cm) were created by adding saline river water. The average composition (mg/litre) of river water at a salinity level of 35 mmho/cm at 25° C was Na⁺ = 7571, K⁺ = 269, Ca²⁺ = 403, Mg²⁺ = 778, Cl⁻ = 1334, SO₄²⁻ = 969, and pH = 7.8. Thirty-day-old seedlings were transplanted in 18-kg porcelain pots with 6 replications. N, P, and K were applied at 120-60-60 kg/ha as urea, single superphosphate, and muriate of potash.

Table 2. Effect of salinity stress on accumulation of Na⁺ by rice plants at peak tillering, West Bengal, India.

Variety	Na ⁺ accumulation (% of dry matter) at ECe (mmho/cm) of		
	3.0	8.0	12.0
CSR-1	0.21	0.29	0.36
CSR-6	0.24	0.35	0.44
CST14-2	0.23	0.27	0.41
CST438-1	0.21	0.29	0.41
CST202-2	0.31	0.38	0.46
CST100-1	0.23	0.33	0.44
Jaya	0.25	0.39	0.50
M1-48	0.27	0.61	1.15

CD at P = 0.05

Variety = 0.018% Na

Salinity = 0.011% Na

Variety × salinity = 0.031% Na.

Dry matter accumulation decreased significantly as soil salinity increased. CSR-1 (var. Damodar) had least dry matter reduction at peak tillering (Table 1). At moderate salinity (8.00 mmho/cm), dry matter reduction in CSR-1 (var. Damodar) was 2%. M-1-48 dry matter production declined 51%.

We analyzed plant tissue accumulation of Na⁺ at peak tillering. Plant tissue accumulated more Na⁺ as soil salinity increased (Table 2). Susceptible varieties accumulated the highest levels, and dry matter production decreased as tissue accumulated more Na⁺.

Results indicated that rice varieties that accumulate less Na⁺ in the shoots at peak tillering stage are more tolerant of salinity than varieties that accumulate higher amounts of Na⁺. \mathcal{L}

Azolla and NH₄NO₃ as organic and inorganic nitrogen sources for rice plants

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We compared azolla-N and NH₄NO₃-N availability to rice plants in the greenhouse. Soil, Dransfelder II, was

Effect of *Azolla mexicana* and NH₄NO₃ treatments on dry matter production and N uptake of rice, Göttingen, West Germany.^a

Treatment	Straw		Grains		Total		Increase ^b (%)					
	DM (g/pot)	N (mg/pot)	DM (g/pot)	N (mg/pot)	DM (g/pot)	N (mg/pot)	1			2		3
							DM (g/pot)	N (mg/pot)	DM (g/pot)	N (mg/pot)	DM (g/pot)	N (mg/pot)
Azolla (t/ha)												
A0	2.16	7.61	1.58	12.91	3.74	20.52	—	—	—	—	—	—
A10	2.70	11.48	1.66	14.95	4.36	26.42	17	29	17	29	30	30
A20	2.92	14.28	1.99	17.56	4.91	31.84	31	55	13	21	28	28
A30	3.47	16.35	2.21	20.35	5.68	36.69	52	79	16	15	27	27
A40	4.02	20.45	2.72	25.46	6.75	45.91	80	124	12	25	32	32
A50	5.55	26.12	3.35	33.56	8.90	59.68	138	191	32	30	39	39
A60	5.95	29.14	4.32	42.70	10.27	71.84	175	250	15	20	43	43
A70	5.00	25.09	3.14	36.01	8.14	61.10	118	198	-21	-15	29	29
CD (5%)	.82	4.82	.54	6.03	1.15	9.31						
N (kg/ha)												
N0	2.16	7.61	1.58	12.91	3.74	20.52	—	—	—	—	—	—
N30	2.81	10.40	1.79	15.21	4.60	25.61	23	25	23	25	26	26
N60	3.24	12.11	2.48	20.43	5.71	32.55	53	56	24	27	30	30
N90	4.83	19.68	2.72	23.23	1.55	42.91	101	109	32	32	37	37
N120	4.98	16.76	3.80	31.58	8.18	48.34	135	136	16	13	35	35
N150	5.37	20.61	3.92	36.59	9.28	57.20	148	179	6	18	37	37
N180	6.03	24.85	4.56	41.26	10.59	66.12	183	222	14	16	38	38
N210	5.74	23.58	4.66	42.33	10.40	65.92	178	221	-2	—	32	32
CD (5%)	0.67	3.50	0.65	5.14	1.01	6.10						

^a Each value is a mean of 4 replications. ^b DM = dry matter production, N = nitrogen uptake. 1 = increase over control, 2 = increase over corresponding control, 3 = N uptake of the applied N (A10 = N30).

andy and had low plant status. Before the 2-kg pots were filled with sieved soil, the soil was mixed with monocalcium-phosphate (MCP) at 90 kg P/ha. Four days after transplanting, 80 kg K/ha as K₂SO₄ and 40 kg Mg/ha as MgSO₄ were applied. *Azolla mexicana* (6/62) from Brazil was grown in water tubs and mixed into the soil 1 wk before transplanting at 10, 20, 30, 40, 50, 60, and 70 t fresh weight/ha. In parallel

treatments, NH₄NO₃ was applied at 30, 60, 90, 120, 180, and 210 kg N/ha, 1 wk after transplanting. Three 50-d-old IR28 seedlings were transplanted in each pot and ripened to maturity. Pots remained submerged throughout the experiment. Grain and straw yield are in the table.

Maximum yield was achieved with 60 t azolla/ha and 180 kg N/ha as NH₄NO₃ (see table). Yields at 10 t azolla/ha and NH₄NO₃ at 30 kg N/ha

were generally comparable. Highest N concentrations in straw and grain were in azolla treatments because there was more growth and yield in NH₄NO₃ treatments. Total N uptake in straw was significantly more in azolla treatments; that for grain was higher in the NH₄NO₃ treatments. The percentage uptake of applied N varied from 27-43% in azolla treatments and 30-38% in NH₄NO₃. ☞

Effect of slow-release urea materials on rice yield

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In Tamil Nadu, rice fields are alternately submerged and drained, which encourages nitrification of applied fertilizers and reduces recovery of fertilizer N by 30-40%. We studied the effect of slow-release N fertilizers on TKM9 grain yield in 1984 kharif.

Soil was sandy loam with pH 4.9 and 288-33-112 kg available NPK/ha. The

Effect of slow-release urea materials on growth, yield components, and grain yield of TKM9 at various N levels, Amhasamudram, India.

N level and urea source ^a	Height (cm)	Panicles/hill	Panicle length (cm)	Panicle wt (g)	Filled grains/panicle	1000-grain wt (g)	Grain yield (t/ha)	Straw yield (t/ha)	Increase (%) over N1 F1	
									N1	F1
N1 F1	81	8.2	19	1.7	70	25.0	5.3	5.6
N1 F2	80	8.8	19	1.8	73	25.6	5.4	5.9	2	2
N1 F3	81	8.7	19	1.8	70	25.4	5.5	6.4	4	4
N1 F4	82	9.2	20	1.9	80	26.2	6.1	6.9	15	15
N2 F1	82	8.6	19	1.7	70	25.2	5.4	5.7	2	2
N2 F2	81	8.6	19	1.7	73	25.4	5.6	6.2	5	5
N2 F3	82	9.2	19	1.7	71	25.5	5.5	6.5	4	4
N2 F4	83	10.0	21	1.9	85	26.2	6.2	1.5	17	17
CD at 5%	1.32	0.87	0.56	0.07	5.88	0.66	0.26	0.99		

^a N levels: N1 = 30 kg, N2 = 75 kg. Urea sources: F1 = prilled urea, F2 = neem cake-coated at 20%, F3 = coal tar-coated at 1%, F4 = USG.